

Research Article

Quality Control and the Performance of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises
in Southwestern Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined the relationship between Quality Control and performance of Small and Medium Sized Enterprises (SMEs) in Southwestern Nigeria. The study was conducted using the survey method. Data for this study was obtained through primary source. The primary source of data was collected through the administration of structured questionnaire to production managers, sales managers and quality control personnel as the respondents selected from the products and services industries such as pharmaceutical and food industry, medical sectors, and financial institutions that fall under SMEs. The sample size of the study was determined by Yamane (1967) formula, since the study has a finite population and the sample size was put at 400 SMEs. Applying proportionality procedure and rounding up to the nearest tens, 200 from manufacturing SMEs and 200 from service SMEs were surveyed. This study adopted both descriptive and inferential statistics. The findings showed that there is a significant relationship between quality control and the performance of SMEs in southwestern Nigeria (Chi-Square 241.207, $P < 0.05$). It is therefore recommended that commitment to total quality control must be backed by action and legislation.

Keywords: Quality, Control, Performance, Commitment, Management

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Introduction

Product or service deficiencies have effect on firm's income. The customer who encounters deficiencies may take action of a cost-related nature: file a complaint, return the product, make a claim, or file a lawsuit, the customer also may publicize the deficiency and its source. Such actions by multiple customers can do serious damage to the company. Quality also have effect on costs, the cost of poor quality consists of all costs that would disappear if there were no deficiencies- no errors, no rework and so on (Wilkinson, 1996). Example of these kinds of defected product is the well-known case of My Pikin Baby Teething mixture that affected 111 children out of which 84 died in 2009 (New York Times, 2009). This cost of poor quality is shockingly high as National Agency for Food, Drug and Administration (NAFDAC) closed down Barewa Pharmaceutical Company, this menace can be addressed with implementation of quality control program. It is often noted that most customers consider quality product. In fact, a reputation for producing quality products is often a major marketing issue. Quality is not just of concern in manufactured products, it is important in banking, hospital care, education, air travel, auto repair, postal delivery services and a host of other firms in the service industry (Akinola, 2009).

One of the major roles of the operations manager is to make sure his or her firm delivers a quality product to the right place at the right time and at the right price (Roodhooft and Konings, 1997). In markets, product with superior quality secures superior income through higher market share or premium prices, products or services that are not competitive in features often sold at below-market prices. The few studies existing on quality control are from the developed countries and majorly based on manufacturing processes and comparative analysis. Meanwhile, there is a growing concern hinging on quality control challenges inhibiting the ability of Nigerian SMEs to catch up with their foreign counterparts. While there is dearth of literatures on quality control in relation to small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs) in developing countries, the existing literature in Nigeria have concentrated on quality control of services in relation to financial institutions (Akinola, 2009). Therefore, this study examined quality control and SMEs nexus in Southwestern Nigeria.

A study like Quality control provides a guide towards evaluating the gains of implementing a quality program both for organizations who have done that and those that are still in the process. It provides an opportunity to critically evaluate every quality program in line of what benefit it will yield. Policy and quality control decision makers like legislators will need this to help enhance their decisions in respect to the subject.

Literature Review

Concept of Quality

Quality has become a strategic weapon being used by industries. A firm with good quality has the tendency to have market share above its competitors. Many manufacturing and service industries have realized the importance of quality. Quality has been defined by scholars and practitioners in different ways. There is no consensus on the definition of quality. Some people view quality as performance to standards; others view it as meeting the customer's needs or satisfying the customers.

Bilich and Neto (2000) stated that quality as a macro-function of institutions must be present in the day to day administration such as establishment of policies, decision process, selection of personnel, allocation of resources, definition of priorities and service delivery to satisfy customers' requirements. Hoyer, Chandy, Dorotic, Krafft, and Singh, (2010) defined quality as two levels concept: level one consists of producing products or delivering services whose measurable characteristics satisfy a fixed set of specifications, and level two refers to products and services that satisfy customer expectations for consumption

Chen, (2008) stated that quality is more than conformance to specifications. Quality management's promise is to provide products and services which are not only better than the competitors', but more reliably and predictably so. The result is more sales, fewer problems, less wasted time and materials, higher revenue, higher profit, and even happier employees (Santos-Vijandeand Alvarez-Gonzalez, 2007; FolopoulosandPsomas, 2010; Monday, Akinola, OlogbenlaandAladeraji, 2015).

Quality Control

Quality control is the price of doing business - good business- and the SME is no exception. Quality control or QC for short is a process by which entities review the quality of all factors involved in production. International Standard Organisation (ISO) 9000 defines quality control as "A part of quality management focused on fulfilling quality requirements".

According to Sihotang and Zebedeus, (2015) "Quality Control is defined as an industrial management technique by means of which products of uniform acceptable quality are manufactured, it is concern mainly with making things right rather than discovering and rejecting those made wrong". Quality control determined what, when and how much to inspect and what measures to take so that defective items are not produced. It is preventive rather than a corrective measure. Quality Control is a process that is used to ensure a certain level of quality in a product or service. It might include whatever

actions a business deems necessary to provide for the control and verification of certain characteristics of a product or services. Most often it involves thoroughly examining and testing the quality of products or the results of service. The basic good of this process is to ensure that the products or services that are provided meet specific requirements and characteristics such as being dependable, safe and fiscally sound. One simple way to control the quality is to conduct 100% inspection (Waldman, 1994). Quality control refers to those features, attributes or variables of the product that determine the satisfaction or dissatisfaction of customers. Quality control (QC) is vital to any kind of business, it does not matter if you are selling products or services, the value of these things are all determined by their quality.

In modern business the role of QC to the success of business, SMEs inclusive cannot be over emphasized. Within a quality control plan, manufacturing businesses would simply crank on products, package and then ship them. However, one of the biggest problems any business can face is defective or shoddy products. As a customer, when you spend hard earned money on something, you expect it to perform as advertised. Inspectors will be provided with lists and descriptions of unacceptable product defects such as cracks or surface blemishes for example. Quality control emphasizes testing of products to uncover defects and reporting to management who make the decision to allow or deny product release. For contract work particularly awarded by government agencies quality control issues are among the top reasons for not reviewing a contract (Harari, 1993).

A business quality control (QC) reputation is important for SMEs success. If potential customers hear nightmares about your products or services, you are not likely to remain in business very long. Even if you make improvements, it can take a long time to repair a bad reputation. This can go the other way as well, if happy customers hear about the value and quality of your business products or services you will inevitably sell more. Having an excellent reputation can sustain a business if they experience short term problems. For example, you may sell products that people have come to depend on. If you establish a reputation for having superior products, people are likely to be more forgiving if they occasionally buy something that is sub-part. As long as you have an effective guarantee, your business can still prosper (Grant, Mergen, and Widrick, 2002).

Small and Medium Scale Enterprises

According to the World Bank (2013), SMEs are defined based on the size of the enterprise in terms of the total number of employees and/ or total assets value. SMEs and large firms can be differentiated based on the aforementioned criteria. However,

the definition of SMEs can be viewed from different perspectives, depending on the organization or country.

The American definition of small-scale business is one with fewer than 100 employees while the medium enterprise has less than 500 employees. In general, the European Union (EU) and a large number of OECD, transition and developing countries set the upper limit of employees' size in the SMEs between 200-250 (Obokoh, Monday and Ojiako, 2014).

Mukumba, (2014) define medium enterprises as firms with less than 250 employees and having less than €50 million turnover or not more than €43 million balance sheet total. A small enterprise refers to firms having less than 50 employees, less than €10 million turnover and/or not more than €10 million balance sheet total.

Stork and Esselaar (2006) report several definitions of SMEs based on different African countries. In Ghana, SMEs referred to firm that have six (6) to ninety-nine (99) number of employees and have not more than 2.5 billion Ghana Cedi (¢) of fixed assets (excluding land and buildings). In South Africa, SMEs are defined as distinct and separate business entities, including cooperative enterprises and non-governmental organizations that are self-managed by a single owner or more which includes its branches or subsidiaries, if any. In Cameroon, SMEs are defined as firms that have turnover value of not less than 1 billion Cameroon Franc (cfa), and accrued investments are not more than 500 million cfa, its short-term credit is not more than 200 million cfa and it has at least 5% owners of the capital and managers are Cameroonians.

Moreover, the Nigeria National Council on Industry (NNCI) in 2002 described small business unit as one whose total investment including working capital but excluding cost of land is above ₦1.5 million but not exceeding ₦50 million, and with a workforce of 11 to 100 people. NCI defined medium-sized firms as those with assets between ₦50 million and ₦200 million, including working capital but excluding cost of land, and number of employees between 101 and 300 (Atawodi and Ojeka, 2012).

In the same vein, Salunkhe, Ramachandran, and Brown (2002) defined small enterprises in Nigeria as enterprises with total assets above US\$100,000 but below/equal to US\$3 million, and a number of employees between 10 and 50. He described medium enterprises as having total assets above US\$15million, with a workforce of 50 to 300 people. Fabayo (2009) divided small scale business in Nigeria into three sectors namely: Production sector (including agricultural processing, manufacturing, and mining), Service sector; and trading sector (including wholesales and retails).

According to Mostafa, Wheeler and Jones (2005) definition varies from country to country. The definitions are required to serve as the policies which govern the sector. Therefore, definition varies from country to country, from one industrial grouping to another and from one financial situation to the other. Generally some parameters are used singly or in combination, (Cohen and Morrison, 2004; Lshengoma and Kappel. 2004) there are capital investment of plant and machinery, number of worker employed and volume of production or turnover of business (Johnson andSchaltegger, 2016).

Different authors have usually given different definition to this category of business, SMEs have indeed not been spared with the definition problem that is usually associated with concepts which have many components. The definition of firm by size values among researchers. Some attempt to use the capital assets while others use skill labour and turnover level. Others define SMEs in terms of their legal status and method of production (Abort & Quartet, 2010). Storey, and Tether (1998) tries to sum up the danger or using size to define the status of firm by stating that in some sectors all firms may be regarded as small, whilst in other sectors there are possibly no firms which are small.

In 2003, the small and medium scale enterprises development agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN) defined small-scale enterprises as those with assets not more than ₦50 million (excluding cost of land but including working capital), and not more than 100 employees, while medium enterprises have assets not more than ₦200 million and not more than 300 employees (Obokoh, 2008; Monday James-unam, 2012. Most recently, SMEDAN in collaboration with the national bureau of statistics (NBS) put up the National Policy on Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises(MSMEs) 2010), and adopts a classification of SMEs (Table 1) SMEs therefore are those enterprises whose total assets (excluding land and building) are above five million naira, but not exceeding five hundred million naira, with a total work force of between 10 and 199 employees

Table 1: Classification of micro, small and medium enterprises in Nigeria

Size category (N' million)	Employees	Asset-Excluding land & building
Micro enterprises	Less than 10	Less than 5
Small enterprises	10 to 49	5 to less than 50
Medium enterprises	50 to 199	50 to less than 500

Source: National policy on MSMEs (2010)

However, the NBS in its agreement with the World Bank, over the same period, defined small scale enterprises as one with project cost not exceeding ₦300, 000 and with cost per job created not more than ₦7,500. Yet some states and institutions in Nigeria have reduced the capital base for the industry to as low as ₦150,000 and ₦250,000 respectively (Dotun, 2015).

Empirical Review of Studies

Kaynak (2003) investigated the relationship between total quality management practices and their effects on firms' performance in the US using survey. TQM was measured by training, management leadership, employee relations, quality data and reporting, supplier relationship, process management, and product/ service design. And performance was measured using perceptual measures of financial performance, quality performance, and inventory management performance. Employing structural equation model (SEM), the results showed that there exists positive relationship among TQM practices, and the practices had significant effects on various performance levels of firms; inventory management performance, quality performance, and financial and market performance.

Gustafsson, Nilsson and Johnson (2003) studied the impact of quality practices on customer satisfaction and business results: product versus service organizations. They researched inside organizations to analyze and investigate how key internal quality practices of product versus service organizations (employee management, process orientation, and customer orientation) influence customer satisfaction and business results. Using a national quality survey from 482 companies in Sweden, their analysis shows that for product organizations, internal quality practices influence customer satisfaction and business results primarily through an organization's customer orientation. For service organizations, both customer and process orientation impact customers directly, and employee management has a direct impact on business results. The research also supports the claim that organizations with a quality foundation are in a better position to adopt a customer orientation.

Al-Mubarak, (2016) investigated application of TQM principles in small and medium firms in Riyadh city using survey. TQM was measured by six main principles of focus on customer, continuous improvement, making decisions based on facts, participation of all stakeholders, team approach, and error preventions. The researcher randomly selected 210 owners or managers of enterprises and administered the questionnaire with a brief idea about the study to help them to fill in the questionnaire correctly. Of the 210 questionnaire administered, 150 questionnaires were analyzed through descriptive statistics; Measures of central tendency and measures of dispersion.

Inferential statistics were performed in terms of measures of Pearson correlation, analysis of variance, and stepwise regression, one sample T-test, F-test and Chi-Square. Descriptive Statistics results showed, in general, that application of TQM principles varies between medium to high rate and the Inferential Statistics results showed that two principles, have significant statistical relationships which are focus on customer and continuous improvement.

Kafetzopoulos, Gotzamani, and Psomas (2013) studied quality practices and performance in Greek restaurants. They focused on the application of quality practices through the ISO 9001 standard implementation in Greek restaurants. The study evaluated the ISO 9001 effectiveness based on achievement of the standard's prescribed objects; secondly, it determined the critical factors that have a significant impact on ISO 9001 effectiveness; and thirdly it assessed the three dimensions of restaurants' performance, namely food quality, operational performance and business performance. The method used was primary research through an appropriate structured questionnaire focusing on 42 restaurants where the ISO 9001 standard has already been put into practice.

Alsughayir (2014) examined the impact of quality practices on productivity and profitability in the Saudi Arabian dried date industry. Analyzing the data using correlation, SEM, and regression analyses revealed that the factors with the greatest impact on productivity and profitability were quality measurement, benchmarking, employee focus, training, and supplier relations. The findings indicated that productivity serves as a mediator for the link between profitability and quality management. He opined that Saudi date producers should consider paying more attention to quality management aspects of the manufacturing process and provides greater management support for quality measurement, benchmarking, and other quality programs.

Mwaniki and Okibo (2014) examined the impact of TQM practices on the performance of banks in Nigeria. Three banks were selected randomly. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to analyse the data, the study showed that the quality of workers employed determine to a very large extent the survival of any bank; also that the application of TQM is not an immunity against distress but a preventive mechanism.

Akinola (2009) examined quality control of services in the Nigerian banking industry, using stratified random and stratified purposive sampling techniques in selecting a total of 27 banks and 135 customers respectively. The study involved questionnaire administration as well as focus group discussion. The data collected were analysed

using descriptive statistic and the study discovered among others that reliability, responsiveness, inexpensive waiting time, competence, courtesy, credibility and communication are major determinants of service quality. It also revealed that epileptic power supply, unstable economic policies, un-conducive working environment, and network servers' failures constituted the major problems facing good quality services in the bank industry.

Monday, Olusegun and Bajomo (2015) investigated the impact of total quality management principles on performance of Nigeria organisations using the Nigeria Banking Industry as a case study. Data was collected from 210 respondents, and correlation analysis and multiple linear regression were employed to analyse the data. The results showed that TQM practices had positive and significant relationship with employee performance, quality performance, and financial performance of the banking organisations. The study concluded that total quality management had significant effect on corporate performance of Nigerian money deposit banks.

From the discussion on the empirical analysis of relevant variables to the study, it is clear that although studies had been conducted locally and by foreign authors on TQM and QMP, but the major construct used in their analysis are the essential variables to be considered in the Quality control and SMEs firms' performance analysis. This study will fill this gap since there is dearth of extant literature and empirical studies on the impact of quality control on the growing SMEs business in Nigeria.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework for this study shows the relationship between the factors influencing Quality Control and Quality Control elements; this is based on established relationships in the Quality Control literature and performance. This relationship could be either direct or indirect, and this study will analyse both relationships, the rectangular shapes at the right hand corner represents the QC elements or constructs which are responsible for QC activities represented by the rectangular shapes in the middle which translated to SMEs performance represented by rectangular shape at the left hand side corner. The QC elements have significance relationship with quality control activities and SMEs performance as indicated in the Figure 1.

Elements of Quality Control

Figure 1 Conceptual model for the Research (Source: Adapted with modification from Mohammadi, (2014)

Methodology

The study area comprises of the six States in the Southwestern Nigeria. This is so because of the higher number of SMEs that operates their businesses in the area and opportunities of easy access to these firms and their employees. The study was

conducted using survey method. Data for this study was obtained through primary source. The primary source of data was collected through the administration of structured questionnaire to production managers, sale managers and quality control personnel as the respondents selected from the products and services industries such as pharmaceutical and food industry, medical sectors, and financial institutions that fall under SMEs.

The total population of registered SMEs in the Southwestern Nigeria was put to 7,474 breaks down as follows: Lagos 4,535, Ogun 546, Oyo 1,394, Ondo 610, Osun 100, Ekiti 285 (SMEDAN Industrial Directory, 2010). Based on the work of Bowale and Akilo (2012) as well as Nana, Asuming-Brempong and Nantui (2013), the study was focused on SMEs from both manufacturing and service industries for the purpose of generalization.

The sample size of the study was determined by Yamane and Ito (1996) formula, since the study has a finite population. According to Israel, and Lamm, (2012) the more heterogeneous a population, the larger the sample size required to obtain a given level of precision. Since this study is made up of heterogeneous population and employs continuous data, the acceptable level of precision (margin of error) is five per cent (Kotrlík & Higgins 2001). Given the

$$n = \frac{N}{\{(1 + N(e^2))\}} = \frac{7474}{\{(1 + 7,474(0.05^2))\}} = 379.7$$

Therefore, the Yamane's formula gives the sample size as 380 SMEs. In order to compensate for non-response which often arise in the survey research, the target population for this study were put at 400 SMEs. Applying proportionality procedure and rounding up to the nearest tens, 200 from manufacturing SMEs and 200 from service SMEs were surveyed. Data were collected from quality control managers and / or production / operation managers and other managers who have knowledge of past and present organizational practices relating to quality control in the companies.

From each firm, a manager was chosen and this gave a total of 400 respondents who participated in the survey.

This study adopted non parametric analysis method. In addition, descriptive and inferential statistics were equally employed. The descriptive statistical tools include frequency, percentage and Friedman Ranking test while Spearman correlation test and Ordinal Logit Model were the inferential statistics used.

Research Findings

Performance of SMEs after Implementation of Quality Control Measures in Southwestern Nigeria

Results from Friedman’s Mean Rank Test of 10 indices that showed the perceived ranking of SMEs performance by entrepreneurs in southwestern Nigeria is shown in Table 2, results showed that performance of SMEs in Nigeria varies depending on different measures used by entrepreneurs in the sector. Performance of SMEs was noticeable in high increase and improvement in sales (6.21), patronage (6.19), quality program (6.17), and decrease in the number of products with defects, errors and failures (5.86). With respect to performance such as employee turnover (4.15) and customer satisfaction (4.65), the performance is still generally low relative to SMEs performance in the area of number of employees participating on quality teams (5.17). This therefore showed that there is a significant relationship between quality control and the performance of SMEs in southwestern Nigeria (Chi-Square 241.207, $P < 0.05$) as indicated in Table 2

Table 2: Levels of Quality Control Implementation by SME firms in Nigeria

Levels of QC Implementation	Friedman’s Rank	Mean
Leadership/ Top Management Commitments	4.94	
Ethical Requirement	4.06	
Process Management	4.03	
Human Resource	5.02	
Training	4.36	
Monitoring	3.62	
Continuous Improvement	5.19	
Competence	4.17	
N	302	
Chi-square	170.229	
Df	7	
Asymp. Sig.	0.000	

Source: Field Survey, 2018

Table 3: Performance of SMEs after implementing quality control program in Nigeria

	STATEMENT	Friedman's Mean Rank	
1	Our firm achieved high increased in patronage	6.19	2 nd
2	The numbers of products/service defects, errors, or failures found by the customer have decreased	5.86	4 th
3	The number of customer complaints has decreased	5.78	6 th
4	Our financial results have been improving	5.80	5 th
5	Our quality program has improved our business performance in general	6.17	3 rd
6	Customers referral rate has increased	5.02	8 th
7	The number of employees participating on quality teams has increased	5.17	7 th
8	Employee satisfaction has increased	4.65	9 th
9	Employee turnover has decreased	4.15	10 th
10	Productivity has increased through sales	6.21	1 st
	N	302	
	Chi-Square	241.207	
	Df	9	
	Asymp. Sig.	0.000	

Source: Field Survey 2016

Pearson Correlation Analysis of the Relationship between Quality Control and SME's Performance

The Relationship between quality control and performance of SMEs is presented in Table 4. The relationship was determined by Pearson's correlation coefficient ranking test at 5% level of significance. Quality control was represented by its elements such as leadership commitment, ethical requirement, process management, human resource, training, monitoring, continuous improvement and competence. From the results, all the measures of quality control, with the exception of leadership commitment and process management, are positively related to performance of SMEs. Leadership commitment and process management are negatively related to performance of SMEs. Also, most of the measures of quality control, with the exception of leadership commitment, training and continuous improvement were not significantly ($p > 0.05$) related to performance of SMEs. This result implies that leadership commitment ($r = -0.198$, $p < 0.05$), training ($r = 0.166$, $p < 0.05$) and continuous improvement ($r = 0.127$, $p < 0.05$) were related but not significant.

The results imply direct relationship between performance and employees training and continuous improvement by SMEs. Meanwhile, the negative sign associated with leadership commitment implies indirect relationship and implies leadership in itself is not sufficient to drive performance of SMEs.

Findings of this study are in line with some of the existing study (Kaynak, 2003, Monday, Olusegun and Bajomo 2015) that itemised the following elements as a measure of firm’s performance. They all measured quality management practice (QMP) with training, management leadership, employee relations, quality data and reporting, supplier relationship, process management, and product/ service design. Their results showed that there exists positive relationship among TQM practices, and the practices had significant effects on various performance levels of firms; inventory management performance, quality performance, and financial and market performance.

In addition, the finding showed that if small and medium scale enterprises can incorporate quality control measure it will improve their financial and non-financial performance in the short and long run.

SMEs stands to benefit a lot with adequate and effective incorporation of quality control system as it will increase sales, promote high level of patronage and referral rate, reduce waste and scrap, reduce variation in product output, reduce customers’ complaint and decrease employees turn over.

Table 4: Correlation Analysis between Quality Control and SME’s Firms Performance

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1	1								
2	0.174*	1							
3	0.075	0.333*	1						
4	0.330*	0.583*	0.382*	1					
5	0.308*	0.301*	0.228*	0.439*	1				
6	0.305*	0.209*	0.207*	0.559*	0.668*	1			
7	0.344*	0.372*	0.315*	0.473*	0.679*	0.568*	1		
8	0.393*	0.211*	0.293*	0.430*	0.409*	0.472*	0.561*	1	
9	0.198*	0.065	-0.051	0.095	0.166*	0.106	0.127*	0.045	1

Source: Data Analysis, 2018

*, significant at 5%

1= leadership/top management commitment, 2= ethical requirement, 3= process management, 4= human resource, 5 = training, 6= monitoring, 7= Continuous improvement, 8= competence, 9= performance

Summary and Conclusion

This study investigated the impact of quality control on performance of small and medium scale enterprises in Southwestern Nigeria. The statistical analysis showed that there was a significant relationship between the quality control practices and SME's performance. Also, findings provide empirical backing that successful implementation and practice of quality control in SMEs will boost performance and survival of these firms. Commitment to total quality control must be backed by action and legislation.

References

- Akinola, G.O. (2009). Quality Control of Services in the Nigerian Banking, *African Research Review*, 3(3),181-203
- Al-Mubarak, M. M. (2016). Challenges of going global for SMES. *International Journal of Innovation and Knowledge Management in the Middle East and North Africa*, 5(1), 213-232
- Alsughayir, A. (2014). Barriers to TQM Implementation within a Private Medical Services Organizations in Saudi Arabia. *International Journal of Business Administration*, 5(3), 117-131.
- Atawodi, O. W., andOjeka, S. A. (2012). Factors that affect tax compliance among small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in North Central Nigeria. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 7(12), 87-101.
- Bilich, F., andNeto, A. A. (2000). Total quality management: quality macrofunction model for banks. *Total Quality Management*, 11(1), 5-15.
- Bowale, K., andAkinlo, A. (2012). Determinants of small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs) performance and poverty alleviation in developing countries: Evidence from South-West Nigeria. *European Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences* 16 (1), 848-863.
- Chen, C. C. (2008). An objective-oriented and product-line-based manufacturing performance measurement. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 112(1), 380-390.

- Chen, H., Liu, J. Y., Sheu, T. S., and Yang, M. (2012). The impact of financial services quality and fairness on customer satisfaction. *Managing Service Quality*, 22(4), 399-421.
- Dotun, F. O. (2015). The key determinants of innovation in small and medium scale enterprises in southwestern Nigeria. *European Scientific Journal, ESJ*, 11(13), 32-46
- Fabayo, J. A. (2009). Small and medium enterprises development strategy: A critical option for sustainable long-term economic development in Nigeria. A paper presented at the first annual international conference on effective management of small and medium scale enterprises for sustainable economic development held at Abraham Adesanya Polytechnic, Ijebu-Ode, August.
- Fotopoulos, C. V., and Psomas, E.L. (2009). The structural relationships between total quality management factors and organizational performance. *The TQM Journal*, 22(5), 539-552.
- Grant, D., Mergen, E., and Widrick, S. (2002). Quality management in US higher education. *Total Quality Management*, 13(2), 207-215.
- Gustafsson, A., Nilsson, L., and Johnson, M. D. (2003). The role of quality practices in service organizations. *International Journal of Service Industry Management*, 14(2), 232-244.
- Harari, O. (1993). Ten reasons why TQM doesn't work. *Management review*, 82(1), 33-45.
- Hoyer, W. D., Chandy, R., Dorotic, M., Krafft, M., & Singh, S. S. (2010). Consumer cocreation in new product development. *Journal of service research*, 13(3), 283-296.
- Israel, G. D., and Lamm, A. J. (2012). Item nonresponse in a client survey of the general public. *Survey Practice*, 5(2), 3089-3099
- Johnson, M. P., and Schaltegger, S. (2016). Two decades of sustainability management tools for SMEs: how far have we come?. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 54(2), 481-505.
- Kafetzopoulos, D., Gotzamani, K., and Psomas, E. (2013). Quality systems and competitive performance of food companies. *Benchmarking: An International Journal*, 20(4), 463-483.

- Kaynak, H. (2003). The Relationship between Total Quality Management Practices and their Effects on Firm Performance. *Journal of Operations Management*, 21(4), 405-435.
- Kotrlik, J. W. K. J. W., and Higgins, C. C. H. C. C. (2001). Organizational research: Determining appropriate sample size in survey research appropriate sample size in survey research. *Information technology, learning, and performance journal*, 19(1), 43-53.
- Monday, J.U. (2012a). Local Content Policy and Performance of Small and Medium Scale Oil Servicing Enterprises in Nigeria. *Unpublished Master of Philosophy (M.Phil) Thesis Ile- Ife: Obafemi Awolowo University.*
- Monday, J.U. (2012b). Materials Management for Business Success: The Case of the Nigerian Bottling Company Plc. *International Journal of Economics and Management Sciences*, 1(7), 50-56.
- Monday, J.U., Olusegun, T.L., andBajomo, O. R. (2015). Are TQM Principles Supporting Organisational Performance in Nigeria? Evidence from Nigerian Banking Industry. Paper Presented at the 2nd International Conference on “*Issues and Challenges in Africa’s Quest for Development*”. O.A.U., Ile-Ife.
- Mostafa, R. H., Wheeler, C., and Jones, M. V. (2005). Entrepreneurial orientation, commitment to the Internet and export performance in small and medium sized exporting firms. *Journal of international entrepreneurship*, 3(4), 291-302.
- Mukumba, T. (2014). Overcoming SMEs challenges through critical success factors: A case of SMEs in the Western Cape Province, South Africa. *Economic & Business Review*, 16(1), 7-18.
- Mohammadi, M. R. (2014). The Effect of Total Quality Management Aspects on Organizational Performance in Iran's Oil Industry. *Kuwait Chapter of the Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review*, 3(5), 24-37.
- Mwaniki, C., andOkibo, B. W. (2014). Effects of total quality management on financial performance in the banking sector: a case study of national bank of Kenya. *IOSR Journal of Economics and Finance (IOSR-JEF)*, e-ISSN, 2321-5933.

- Nana, Y. C. F., Asuming-Brempong, S., and Nantui, M. F. (2013). Analysis of cocoa-based agricultural knowledge and information systems in the eastern region of Ghana. *Russian Journal of Agricultural and Socio-Economic Sciences*, 14(2), 12-27
- National Policy on MSMEs. (2010), *Survey Report on Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) in Nigeria*. Abuja.
- Obokoh, L.O. (2008). Small and Medium Sized Enterprises Development under Trade Liberalization: A Survey of Nigerian Experience. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 3 (12), 92-10.
- Obokoh L.O., Monday, J.U., and Ojiako, U. (2014). The Effects of Microfinance Banks on Indigenous Manufacturing SMEs' Access to Finance in Nigeria. *8th International Business Conference Proceedings (4-20: Financial Management and Investments Tract)*. Swakopmund: North-West University.
- Roodhooft, F., and Konings, J. (1997). Vendor selection and evaluation an activity based costing approach. *European journal of operational research*, 96(1), 97-102.
- Santos-Vijande, M.L., and Alvarez-Gonzalez, L.I. (2007). Innovativeness and Organizational Innovation in total quality oriented Firms: The Moderating Role of Market Turbulence. *Technovation*, 27 (2007), 514-532.
- Sihotang, R. B., and Zebedeus, Z. V. (2015). Relationships Between Total Quality Management Practices, Organizational Culture and Teacher's Performance: Study from Seventh Day Adventist High Schools in West Indonesia. *International Research Journal of Business Studies*, 6(2), 31-46
- Steven W. J. (2012). *Operations Management* (11th Ed.). New York: McGraw-Hill Company.
- Stork, C., and Esselaar, S. (2006). Towards an African e-index: SME e-access and usage across 14 African countries. *Research ICT Africa* 1(1), 13-27
- Storey, D. J., and Tether, B. S. (1998). Public policy measures to support new technology-based firms in the European Union. *Research policy*, 26(9), 1037-1057.
- Waldman, D. A. (1994). The contributions of total quality management to a theory of work performance. *Academy of Management review*, 19(3), 510-536.

- Wheeler, C. H. (2005). Job flows and productivity dynamics: Evidence from its manufacturing. Working paper 2005-2007, *Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis*.
- Wilkinson, Adrian, and Hugh Willmott (1996). Quality Management, Problems and Pitfalls: A Critical Perspective. *International Journal of Quality & Reliability Management*, 2(1), 26-49
- Yamane, Y., and Ito, D. I. (1996). Feynman- α formula with dead time effect for a symmetric coupled-core system. *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, 23(12), 981-987.